

WOMEN, RELIGION AND HUMAN RIGHTS: AN APPROACH FROM WESTERN LEGAL SYSTEMS

JAIME ROSSELL¹

The Roman saying "Ubi societas, ibi ius" (where there is society, there is law) has its origin in society's need to protect the interests of its citizens through the legal system, which orders and establishes the rules of coexistence in society. On occasions, the set of rights and duties of each citizen, their interests, clash with those of their neighbors, generating conflicts to which the legal system must find the fairest solution.

Nowadays, as a consequence of the religious diversity existing in society, there are conflicts related to belonging to a certain religion and the exercise of fundamental rights. In the case of women, although most of these conflicts are located in certain geographical areas, we must not forget that the position of women, in the vast majority of religions, has changed very little throughout history. A position which, as one author points out, has been used by men "to maintain spaces of power"².

Thus, religious diversity has incorporated certain customary religious or cultural practices, based on patriarchal models, which jeopardize the rights and freedoms won by women in Western society. And although in a secular and democratic State, respect, tolerance, and religious freedom of the individual and of the confessions must be guaranteed, the acceptance of these practices must have the dignity of women as a limit³, even though they may affect the secularizing process of the state or support the fundamentalist discourse of some religious leaders.

¹ Jaime Rossell, PhD, is Professor of Ecclesiastical Law at the University of Extremadura. He is a member of the Commission Adviser of Religious Freedom of the Ministry of Justice and is a member of the Board of Experts of the International Religious Liberty Association and the International Association for the Defense of Religious Liberty (IADRL) based in Bern, Switzerland.

² Parejo Guzmán, MJ., "¿Mujer, pluralismo religioso e igualdad de género?: desafío jurídico en el siglo XXI en España," *Revista de Derecho de la UNED*, no. 23 (2018): 154.

³In Spain, a criminal court in Barcelona sentenced on 12 January 2004 an Imam who published the book "La mujer en el Islam" (Women in Islam). In this book, an excessively sexist interpretation of the Quran is made, justifying the physical violence against women if they are not able to dominate them in the family environment, considering the subjugation of the female figure as something natural. The court ruled that the Imam's right to religious freedom was limited by the right to the moral integrity of the woman who was the target of his speech.

There is a great majority of religions that, with the argument of a divine and superior order, have transmitted "gender stereotypes based on the superiority of men over women, typical of a patriarchal culture"⁴. But this vision, in many cases, is not based on the sacred texts of these confessions. It is the result of an interpretation of these texts by men that responds to the historical reality in which these religions were born and developed.

Nassira Sediri argues that "the underlying idea of the Koran is based on respect between all Muslims, whether men or women, although historical reality has led to the imposition of a unitary patriarchal vision"⁵. In fact, those who defend full equality between men and women and its compatibility with Islam, point out that the Shari'a represented an advance in the situation of women at the time of its promulgation. It is this Islamic spirit that must be defended, by contextualizing it in a new society that has already abandoned patriarchal patterns⁶.

The Quran establishes equal dignity between men and women⁷, although it maintains the primacy of the male in the family and society⁸. As Combalía points out, Islamic law "does not accept equality between men and women, but equity, which consists in giving each of them the rights and duties that correspond to them by virtue of the different roles they play in society... it is not possible to speak of equal rights and duties, but complementary ones"⁹. An idea that was taken up in article 6¹⁰ of the Declaration of Human Rights in Islam, drawn up in Cairo in 1990 by the Organization of the Islamic Conference, and which sets the Shari'a as its main source.

In Judaism, the role of women is also much more restricted than we might suppose and the Torah shows us the important role of women in the history of the Jewish people¹¹. Here too, the sacred texts present men and women as

⁴ Parejo Guzmán, "¿Mujer, pluralismo religioso e igualdad de género?" 180.

⁵ Ibid., 165.

⁶ Vid. Connors, J., *The Women's Convention in the Muslim World*, en VV.AA. (Ed. M. Yamani), "Feminism and Islam. Legal and literary perspectives," (Berkshire: Ithaca Press, 1997), 364.

⁷ Aleyas 3,195 y 4,1.

⁸ Aleyas 2,228 y 4,34.

⁹ Combalía Solís, Z., "¿Igualdad o equidad?: el reconocimiento en Occidente de instituciones islámicas de inspiración patriarcal," *Revista General de Derecho Canónico y Derecho Eclesiástico del Estado*, IUSTEL, 20 (2009), 3.

¹⁰ "(a) Woman is equal to man in human dignity, and has her own rights to enjoy as well as duties to perform, and has her own civil entity and financial independence, and the right to retain her name and lineage.

(b) The husband is responsible for the maintenance and welfare of the family".

¹¹ "the Torah presents us with a myriad of female role models who excel in all areas in their own way. We have Deborah as a judge, who becomes the image of justice and wisdom...; Miriam as an image and example of leadership; the matriarchs as the perfect model of love and family; Esther as a symbol of dedication to the Jewish people, of the fullness of a reigning kingdom and of the tzniut to which men too are obligated; and Ruth as the pivot of love of Torah, the strength of conversion and the desire to seek God." Vid. Gleason, "A. La mujer en el judaísmo: cuatro formas de ver el género," *Enlace Judío*, 10 de marzo de 2021 (<https://www.enlacejudio.com>).

complementary, with different obligations and responsibilities. And although there are currents with different degrees of patriarchalism, there are also reformist movements in which women occupy a very different position. For some time now, there have been women who have held the role of rabbis.

Neither the Second Vatican Council nor the Code of Canon Law distinguishes between believers, men and women, on the basis of their dignity and freedom, or on the basis of their cooperation in the mission of the Church. In this case, "the radical equality of the faithful is a principle which inspires the entire juridical-canonical regulation... it is not a question of inequality in the order of personal juridical status... but exclusively in relation to certain functions"¹². This does not mean, however, that for some time now there has been a growing awareness that this discrimination between men and women is not legal but *de facto*¹³.

As one author has pointed out, it is not easy to find a religious community in which, applying the secular legal categories of equality and non-discrimination, there is complete equality between men and women. The position of men and women differs from one denomination to another. And it is usually more pronounced when we refer to the sphere of the family or to the responsibilities of government and administration of the denomination, as these functions are usually connected to that of leadership in doctrinal matters¹⁴.

"With all the necessary nuances, the path of the religious denominations - doctrinally, legally and politically - (has been) marked above all by men... as something deeply rooted in the very structure - constitutive and functional - of the denominations"¹⁵. One example is the Torah, which, written and interpreted by men, has been inaccessible to women until very recently because they did not have access to study and knowledge of it. In fact, women have never participated in the elaboration of the Halacha, which is the normative part of the sacred texts, not even to regulate those issues that affect them directly, although the rights of women in the field of marriage were recognized, which until the twentieth century were not recognized by the most advanced legislations¹⁶.

¹² Blanco, M., "La mujer en el ordenamiento jurídico canónico," *Revista General de Derecho Canónico y Derecho Eclesiástico del Estado*, IUSTEL, 20 (2009), 6.

¹³ This does not detract from the role that women have played in the Catholic Church over the centuries. One example are the abbesses, women who, as an integral part of their office, possessed important juridical and even political power within the Church. And there are also women - such as the Spanish Teresa of Jesus - who are very important from a doctrinal point of view. In this sense, women's religious congregations are the most obvious example of women's autonomy in a world in which they were predestined to be subordinate to men.

¹⁴ Martínez-Torrón, J., "La igualdad de sexos en el sistema acordado de relaciones entre el Estado español y confesiones religiosas," *Aequalitas: Revista jurídica de igualdad de oportunidades entre mujeres y hombres* (2012), 63-64.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 64.

¹⁶ Vid. Perales Agustí, M., "La mujer en el Derecho y el matrimonio judío," *Revista General de Derecho Canónico y Derecho Eclesiástico del Estado* 20, (2009).

And in the case of the Catholic Church, as one author points out, "despite the active and recognized role of women in its first centuries of existence, the Church was no stranger to the legal and theological institutionalization of discrimination against women, which stemmed from a masculinizing exegesis of biblical texts... and from a strictly paternal and manly idea of God"¹⁷.

This lack of women's participation in the interpretation of sacred texts has long led to the legitimization of practices that violated women's rights. They were prescribed by the sacred texts but were interpretations of them performed exclusively by men. Fortunately, this situation has been changing over time and has to do, in some cases, with the incorporation of women into the work of studying and interpreting the texts.

Two of the areas within religion in which there are often discriminatory situations between men and women refer to the family and to the position or role of women as leaders within the ecclesiastical organization.

From a gender perspective, evangelical and canonical marriage does not create problems. In Jewish and Islamic marriage, on the other hand, there is no legal equality between men and women. This has not prevented some Muslim countries, such as Morocco with the new Family Code (the *Mudawana*) of 2004, from making an effort to modernise and promote human rights in harmony with Islamic tradition and spirit by regulating the position of women and minors in family matters. However, it is clear that in this ongoing reform it is not possible to go against the provisions of the sacred texts, so that sometimes it is not possible to achieve real legal equality. This has led some European countries, which recognize the validity of religious marriages, to limit their civil effects only to the way in which they are celebrated.

The basic problem "is not so much that of the position of women, but the broader problem of the Shari'a's capacity to adapt, of its suitability to be interpreted in accordance with the evolution of society"¹⁸. The problem does not arise in those countries that recognize the validity and efficacy of Islamic family law, but when some of these institutions, such as polygamy or repudiation, are claimed as valid in countries where equality is at the heart of the system.

In these cases, in order to prevent the penetration of this type of institution that violates fundamental values, the legal recourse used by the legal system has been the public order exception. However, we must also be aware that, on occasions, a strict approach in the invocation of public order to prevent the

¹⁷ Vega Gutiérrez, A.Mª., *Díálogos de Teología de Almudí. Algunos acentos del pontificado del Papa Francisco* (2014).

¹⁸ Combalá Solís, Z., "¿Igualdad o equidad?: el reconocimiento en Occidente de instituciones islámicas de inspiración patriarcal," *Revista General de Derecho Canónico y Derecho Eclesiástico del Estado*, IUSTEL, 20 (2009): 16.

recognition of these institutions could, in practice, be detrimental to the rights of the women it is intended to protect.

For this reason, and as a consequence of the growing cultural and religious diversity of our societies, the application of this concept has begun to become more flexible. In Spain, for example, polygamous marriage is not recognized, although it can be recognized as a valid legal institution when it has inheritance effects or when the second wife claims maintenance or a pension. Also in Spain, "our courts continue to consider that repudiation violates public order because it violates the rights of women, because of its private nature..., and because of its revocable nature... but it is recognized if the woman requests it"¹⁹.

Another area in which discrimination against women has been recurrently pointed out has to do with their role in the organizational structure of religions, or as ministers of worship. In the case of Christian churches, the most obvious example is that of the Catholic Church. In 1994, Pope John Paul II, in his Apostolic Letter "Ordinatio sacerdotalis"²⁰, spoke out against women's access to the priesthood. Subsequently, and as a consequence of the ordination in 2002 of seven German Catholic women by an Argentinean bishop, Benedict XVI, then Prefect of the Congregation for the Doctrine of the Faith, issued a General Decree in 2007 condemning with excommunication "latae sententiae" those women who attempted to take holy orders and the bishops who ordained them.

The debate, therefore, seems closed, although it is true that Pope Francis, through the *Motu Proprio Spiritus Domini* of 2021, has recognized the possibility of women exercising the ministry of lector and acolyte. Meanwhile, for some time now he has been encouraging a greater role for women in the governance of the church, incorporating them into the places where important ecclesiastical decisions are made, which is serving as an example in many dioceses.

Protestant churches, on the other hand, have been much more flexible in incorporating women into the priesthood and its governing bodies. They have been incorporated since the mid-1970s and since the 1980s into the episcopate. Similarly, since the 1980s, there have also been women rabbis in Reform Judaism.

For this reason, one author has pointed out that "the struggle for the recognition of women's rights is, in itself, a struggle against the patriarchal culture that dominates most of our societies and world religions"²¹.

¹⁹ Ibid., 26.

²⁰ "Wherefore, in order that all doubt may be removed regarding a matter of great importance, a matter which pertains to the Church's divine constitution itself, in virtue of my ministry of confirming the brethren (cf. Lk 22:32) I declare that the Church has no authority whatsoever to confer priestly ordination on women and that this judgment is to be definitively held by all the Church's faithful".

²¹ Parejo Guzmán, ¿Mujer, pluralismo religioso e igualdad de género?... cit. p. 155.

When there are conflicts related to equality between men and women within religion, international law, through different legal documents, has been very clear in defending the rights of women and guaranteeing their non-discrimination. But, except in cases of violence against women, I believe that we should reject approaches that advocate that the solution to these conflicts should always be the same, as we could be denying the normative value of respect for religious diversity.

Some of the conflicts that exist within religions are generated as a consequence of the rights or duties acquired by the believer, or the exercise of certain practices that are different according to gender. In some of these cases, we must not forget that sometimes it is the woman who voluntarily places herself in a certain position by belonging to or practicing a religion.

The question is whether Western legal systems should apply the principle of equality and non-discrimination interpreted in strictly secular or civil terms, to challenge the internal rules of religious denominations, in which women are subjected to differential or inferior treatment.

In my opinion, the answer must be negative. Otherwise, it would conflict with the right to autonomy and self-organization of the churches, an essential element of the content of the fundamental right to religious freedom. A right which, as the European Court of Human Rights has frequently affirmed, is indispensable for the existence of pluralism in a democratic society²².

As Martínez-Torrón points out, "a state that would seek to apply a secular notion of equality to the internal sphere of the confessions would be ignoring the fact that they are not obliged to organize themselves in the manner of a liberal democracy. Their approaches and the justification for their existence are different... and although many of these denominations have undemocratic hierarchical structures, the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has pointed out on several occasions that the religious freedom of the citizen within the denomination itself, and therefore its legal position, is sufficiently guaranteed from the moment that the citizen has the right to freely leave the denomination at any time..."²³.

Churches have the right to set limits on the exercise of religious freedom by their members. They may impose a uniform religious doctrine and, consequently, also impose corresponding sanctions on members who deviate from it, including expulsion from the religious denomination²⁴.

²² Vid. ECtHR *Serif vs Grecia* de 14 de diciembre de 1999; *Hasan y Chausch vs Bulgaria* de 26 de octubre de 2000; *Iglesia metropolitana de Besaravia vs Moldavia* de 13 de diciembre de 2001 y *Mirolubous y otros vs Letonia* de 15 de septiembre de 2009.

²³ La igualdad de sexos en el sistema acordado..., cit., p. 64

²⁴ Vid. Martínez-Torrón, J., "Los límites a la libertad de religión y creencias en el Convenio de Derechos Humanos," *Revista General de Derecho Canónico y Derecho Eclesiástico del Estado*, IUSTEL, no. 2 (2003): 35.

In case of conflict, Article 9 of the European Convention on Human Rights does not protect any right of dissenters to challenge an ecclesiastical decision before civil courts, because only religious authorities are competent to settle their internal disputes. Limiting or restricting the right to internal autonomy of denominations cannot be done in a discretionary basis, but only in cases where there is a "compelling social need"²⁵. As the ECtHR has pointed out on several occasions, the State cannot legitimately interfere in a purely religious matter that has been settled by the religious community concerned, even where there is a strong division of opinion within that community on the matter. This does not mean that some cultural and religious practices that continue to justify discrimination against women must disappear. We must continue to seek instruments that ensure that religion is not used in civil life as an instrument of male superiority over women or to justify discrimination against women, but without imposing on religious models contrary to their doctrine.

Several international texts have pronounced themselves in this regard. Article 4 of the 1993 Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women prohibits states from invoking custom, tradition or religious considerations to avoid the obligation to prevent, investigate and punish acts of violence against women. Art. 5(a) of the 1981 Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) notes the need for States to intervene to eliminate prejudices and customary practices that reflect a stereotyped role for women but does not call for intervention on religions per se or for changing people's religious beliefs²⁶.

The European Parliament, in its Resolution 2000/2174 on women and fundamentalism, establishes the need to ensure that religion and religious freedom are not used as a tool or excuse to discriminate against women. However, the aim of this document is not to modify the internal regime of religious communities, but to ensure that religious or supposedly religious rules or customs cannot be used as an instrument of discrimination against women, in a secular society that aims to make the principle of equality a reality and effective.

When Asma Jahangir, UN Special Rapporteur on religious freedom, noted in 2010 that "it cannot be considered taboo to demand that women's rights take precedence over intolerant beliefs that are used to justify gender discrimination"²⁷, she meant that women's rights naturally take precedence over religions and beliefs, which are not rights-holders, as women's rights cannot be

²⁵ Vid. ECtHR *Serif vs Grecia* de 14 de diciembre de 1999.

²⁶ Vid. Relación Pastor, E., "Derechos de las mujeres y libertad religiosa: ¿irreconciliables?" *Cuestiones de pluralismo*, vol 1, nº 1 (1er semestre 2021), *Revista del Observatorio del Pluralismo religioso en España* (https://www.observatorioreligion.es/revista/volumen_1/numero_1/index.html).

²⁷ A/65/207, párr. 69.

limited, violated, or undermined in the name of religion. But without imposing civil rules on these religions that modify their autonomy or doctrine.

Religions themselves must adapt to the new social contexts through an interpretation of religious texts adjusted to the social reality in which they operate. Progress towards greater equality and non-discrimination of women within religious confessions requires: a) an effort on the part of religious leaders to adapt the application of texts and norms of sacred origin to current contexts; b) promoting reforms in the internal organization of the denominations that allow women access to positions of responsibility; c) promoting women's rights within the religious communities themselves.

A formidable tool to work in this direction could be education:

- to allow women access to the study of sacred texts and theological studies
- recognizing the possibility for women to become educators of future ministers of worship and religious leaders.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Blanco, M. "La mujer en el ordenamiento jurídico canónico." *Revista General de Derecho Canónico y Derecho Eclesiástico del Estado*, IUSTEL 20 (2009): 6.
- Combalá Solís, Z. "¿Igualdad o equidad?: el reconocimiento en Occidente de instituciones islámicas de inspiración patriarcal." *Revista General de Derecho Canónico y Derecho Eclesiástico del Estado*, IUSTEL 20 (2009): 3.
- Connors, J. *The Women's Convention in the Muslim World*, en VV.AA. (Ed. M. Yamani), "Feminism and Islam. Legal and literary perspectives." Berkshire: Ithaca Press, 1997.
- ECtHR *Serif vs Grecia* de 14 de diciembre de 1999; *Hasan y Chausch vs Bulgaria* de 26 de octubre de 2000; *Iglesia metropolitana de Besaravia vs Moldavia* de 13 de diciembre de 2001 y *Mirolubous y otros vs Letonia* de 15 de septiembre de 2009.
- Gleason, A. "La mujer en el judaísmo: cuatro formas de ver el género." *Enlace Judío*, 10 de marzo de 2021 (<https://www.enlacejudio.com>).
- Martínez-Torrón, J. "La igualdad de sexos en el sistema acordado de relaciones entre el Estado español y confesiones religiosas." *Aequalitas: Revista jurídica de igualdad de oportunidades entre mujeres y hombres* (2012): 63-64.
- Martínez-Torrón, J. "Los límites a la libertad de religión y creencias en el Convenio de Derechos Humanos." *Revista General de Derecho Canónico y Derecho Eclesiástico del Estado*, IUSTEL, no. 2 (2003): 35.
- Parejo Guzmán, MJ. "¿Mujer, pluralismo religioso e igualdad de género?: desafío jurídico en el siglo XXI en España." *Revista de Derecho de la UNED*, no. 23 (2018): 154.
- Perales Agustí, M. "La mujer en el Derecho y el matrimonio judío." *Revista General de Derecho Canónico y Derecho Eclesiástico del Estado* 20, (2009).
- Relaño Pastor, E. "Derechos de las mujeres y libertad religiosa: ¿irreconciliables?" *Cuestiones de pluralismo*, vol 1, nº 1 (1er semestre 2021). *Revista del Observatorio del Pluralismo religioso en España*. https://www.observatorioreligion.es/revista/volumen_1/numero_1/index.html.
- Vega Gutiérrez, A.Mª. *Diálogos de Teología de Almudí. Algunos acentos del pontificado del Papa Francisco*, 2014.